

RESPONSE PAPER**FIRST NAME: NYUMA****LAST NAME: JOE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA- 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: MS Word 2016 on Windows 8

ROADMAP TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

EUCLID takes no chance because they crave for excellence. In spite of what I have learnt about academic writing skills in the past, I was taken aback to the basics of academic writing. My early days in the pursuit of undergraduate and graduate degrees were remarkably ruminated upon, as those days provided the basic foundation for my academic writing skills. But the fact remains that my programme with EUCLID is like a rejuvenation or an animation of my academic writing skills to a much higher level, considering my discipline as a social scientist, who requires to update and sharpen his skills in academic writing. However, I appreciate this style of education I am to imbibe from EUCLID, because this course serves as a stepping stone, not only towards the pursuit of a PhD in Mediation and Conflict Resolution, but also serves as my strongest foundation so far, in the research and writing of quality academic papers, as my mind has since been made up to embrace current and future innovations, in academic writing skills. In essence, this coursepack provides the necessary guidance in the writing of my dissertation and other papers, prescribed by EUCLID.

2) A REVIEW OF PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1 spelling out the rudiments of academic writing, comprises 61 pages, which serves as a one-stop shop that provides the basics required in carrying out academic writing exercise, taking account of major topical areas ranging from essay writing, to the ethics of plagiarism and much more

Essay writing sometimes becomes an issue considering the rigors involved in transmitting an idea on paper, in a manner that it makes sense to the readership. I have learnt that writing down everything you know about a topic is not enough to make a good academic essay, but analyzing and answering the essay's question are crucial. It is therefore central to first and foremost organize your ideas about a given topic, because it helps the writer to shape his ideas and properly adopt a positive roadmap as to how to go about writing the essay, taking into account the relevance of time, as well.

The coursepack also made the ethics of plagiarism a concern, which EUCLID consistently warned students against, thus drawing their attention to the use of paraphrasing and citations and the fact of acknowledging or giving credit to the ideas of other author(s), hence plagiarism is a serious academic offence that has serious consequences (EUCLID 2019, 5). It is therefore advised that students restate their ideas in a manner, that it does not resemble the original words of the author quoted. However, it is also essential to limit the use of quotation, as too much use of it may appear as if it is not your own research (EUCLID 2019, 7). Paraphrasing or generating ideas and information of an author in your own words that is the accurate representative of what the author originally wrote, is better practice, provided it does not present a close paraphrase from the source. It is therefore advised that when using the exact words of the author, we use quotation marks or reiterate the point in our own words. In a nutshell, good academic writing cites its sources, uses only high-quality sources and guarantees the sources in question support the argument the author is making (Your Dictionary 1996, 2). In essence, plagiarism could be viewed as a form of academic theft which must be avoided entirely in this programme.

Another area of interest to me cited in this coursepack is the use of basic words that are similar which I have not been having problems with, but however, bringing my attention to these basic words such as "its" and "it's", "yours" and "You're", underscores the relevance of their usage in this course. But for words like "that" and "which", I have been using them interchangeably, till now that I have noted the distinction. "That" precedes only restrictive phrases, while "which" usually precedes nonrestrictive phrases (EUCLID 2019, 19).

The other area that captivated my attention and warrants sharing, relates to the differences between the American and British English in terms of spelling and pronunciation. In retrospect, I discovered during my previous academic studies, that I imbibed the Standard British English (SBE) but have realized that both versions are absolutely accepted (EUCLID 2019, 14). The recognition of this rule would be quite helpful to me in my studies at EUCLID, because the Standard British English which I will adopt, is much more flexible and comfortable for me.

Perusing the sample corrections, I clearly found myself wanting in a few areas during my previous academic writing, particularly with regard to the writing of

dissertations, journal articles for publication as well as other relevant official write-ups like the preparation of Cabinet Memoranda and policy briefs to guide my minister in his engagements with H.E. the President on foreign policy issues. This clearly infers that, for instance, the current approach to preparing position papers in the public sector requires a postmortem that would crave for standard and error-free submissions, which will not just follow a chosen format and style, but takes into account, the type of English Language to be adopted as well. The undeniable truth is that my studies at EUCLID will not only induct me into the rudiments of my course area, which is Doctorate in Mediation and Conflict Resolution, but will also assist me to graduate with multivariate techniques in managing the two strands of the English Language. As a diplomat who has worked extensively in Africa and currently in Asia, South Korea to be specific, where American English is widely adopted, I have no alternative left but to ensure a configurative recalibration of my intellect, to better fit within the global frame, required of a diplomat who is bound to be adaptive and flexible. In my extra time, I vow to be perusing this area of study, for better acclimatization.

3) ADOPTION OF CHICAGO STYLE OF REFERENCING

During analysis of the section on the crib sheet, I discovered that the crib sheet is a useful tool that indicates to students how to do in-text citation, the listing of references / sources, as well as directing them to be mindful in the use of punctuation in academic writing. In essence, the Chicago style is widely used in EUCLID in the writing of response and major papers, as well as dissertations. I noted attentively the need to spell out in the text geographical terms such as countries, postal addresses, mountains, valleys, rather than abbreviating them.

In a bid to guide students in writing the papers prescribed by EUCLID, the coursepack left no stone unturned when it provided the various forms capitalization may follow, which are full caps, head caps, or sentence caps and further explained their usage. It further emphasizes that in using head caps, the first and last words of all nouns, pronouns, adjectives and conjunctions are capitalized, whereas articles such as “an”, “a”, “the” and propositions such as “against”, “between”, “in”, “of” as well as conjunctions such as “and”, “for”, “nor”, “or”, “yet” and initiatives like “to” are not capitalized (EUCLID 2019, 45). It is also permissible to capitalize the first word of a title or heading, the first words after a colon and proper noun but not to compound nationalities and ethnicities such as “African American”.

Further exploring the coursepack, I discovered and pledged that several things I ignored in the past will no longer be ignored in my essay writing. For instance the use of italics and quotation marks which are adopted to highlight and translate words in a language foreign to a reader as well as writing out numbers and date when opening a sentence and more importantly, to desist from mixing numerals with written numbers when they refer to similar things. It is also advised not to mix numbers that are spelt out with symbols, the term for the symbol should be written out, e.g. \$200. But interestingly, the Chicago style for percentages states that it is proper to write 45%.

By and large, in analyzing the rudiments of essay writing, I have learnt so many things I never knew, some of which have been discussed above. Additionally, the use of quotation in citation as well as other rules guiding the use of quotations, much of which are prescribed by the Chicago Manual, the Turabian Manual and the American Psychological Association (APA) Publication Manual, are all very significant to my studies as they will be sourced, read and digested properly and every effort will be made to capture the rules bordering on the use of footnotes, especially Chicago footnotes and endnotes, as well as the use of bibliography and its applicability.

In a nutshell, I would state unequivocally that this course will be very helpful to me as it has sharpened my skills in academic writing for which I am grateful to EUCLID University, such that at this initial stage in my travail to secure a Doctorate Degree in Mediation and Conflict Resolution, almost every information that is relevant to my survival in this programme, has been made available to me.

In spite of the fact that I have acquired some significant experience in academic writing at graduate level for different audience and purposes, including for journal articles adopting mainly the APA style, I have noted with much caution that I would be operating within the remit of EUCLID University's prescription, in the pursuit of my Doctorate degree. Such rapid academic metamorphosis, realistically, should not remain a novelty to me because in life the only permanent condition is change, especially this positive change, which I perceive as even much more rewarding, in spite of being a more tasking experience.

4) CONCLUSION

Over the past decade, I have acquired some experience at undergraduate and graduate levels in essay writing and as a Civil Servant/Diplomat, which has been very helpful to me in the preparation of policy briefs and position papers to guide my minister in his engagement with H.E. the President. I have also published a few articles and a book of reading co-authored with one or my lead assessors in my graduate programme, which was the most rewarding academic experience undertaken with the assistance of this erudite professor whom I can aptly describe as a rare scholar of our time and a generational pathfinder who believes in quality. However, my invitation into new corridors of academia such as the Chicago Style and the Turabian Manual of Style, will be even more rewarding, as it will add to my academic credentials.

REFERENCES

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